

Model-free data-efficient inference of network connectivity from time series with subReservoir Computing

Pablo Rojas¹, Marie Kempkes¹, Claudia Arbeitman^{1,2,3}, Oreste Piro^{1,4,5} & Martin E. Garcia¹

¹*Theoretical Physics and Center for Interdisciplinary Nanostructure Science and Technology (CIN-SaT), University of Kassel, Kassel, Germany*

²*CONICET Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas, Buenos Aires, Argentina*

³*GIBIO–Universidad Tecnológica Nacional-Facultad Regional Buenos Aires, Buenos Aires, Argentina.*

⁴*Departament de Física, Universitat de les Illes Balears, Palma de Mallorca, Spain*

⁵*Institut Mediterrani d'Estudis Avançats, IMEDEA (CSIC–UIB), Esporles, Spain*

Complex dynamical systems are often composed of interacting elements whose dynamics is determined by the underlying network connecting the nodes. The inference of directed links in a network from observed time series is an ill-posed inverse problem. Current approaches require either large amounts of data and computation, or restrictive assumptions that alleviate this requirement, such as a mathematical model to describe the dynamics, both of which limit their application to the study of natural systems. Here, we present a model-free and data-efficient method for the inference of network connectivity from observed time series of the individual nodes. The method leverages the training and approximation properties of a new architecture for the Reservoir Computing recurrent neural network paradigm, which we termed subReservoir Computing, in order to learn dynamical systems while encoding the directed links in the readout layer. We demonstrate that this approach naturally tackles the inference of a wide range of network connectivity schemes and delayed interactions using a single-instance time series as a training set and minimizing hyperparameter tuning. The new method paves the way for massive network inference from experimental data with minimal assumptions.

Networks emerge pervasively across nature, science and engineering. Many systems of interest in diverse disciplines—from neuroscience and molecular biology to economics and social science—can be described as networks of interacting nodes¹. In such systems, global behavior is often shaped not only by the properties of individual components but crucially by the pattern of connections among them. Deciphering network

structure is therefore a fundamental prerequisite for understanding a broad range of phenomena, including brain function, biochemical and metabolic pathways, allosteric communication in proteins, and socio-economic dynamics.

Various strategies have been developed to reconstruct networks from data. One family of approaches involve controlled experimental interventions, in which one or more variables are perturbed to infer causal relationships based on differences between observational and interventional distributions^{2,3,4}. While such interventions are essential for establishing formal causality, they are often impractical or infeasible in complex systems. As a result, a number of methods have been proposed to infer causal structure from purely observational data, relying on statistical asymmetries or assumptions about noise distributions⁵.

A particularly rich source of information is time series data, where the temporal ordering of observations provides a natural structure for inferring directionality. This idea underpins methods such as Granger causality⁶, which evaluates whether past values of one time series improve the prediction of another via autoregressive modeling. Extensions of this concept accommodate nonlinearities^{7,8}, point processes, and non-stationary dynamics. Similarly, information-theoretic approaches such as transfer entropy^{9,10} quantify the reduction in uncertainty of a node's future state due to knowledge of another node's past. Correlation-based methods^{11,12,13,14,15,16}, often applied in neuroscience, use lagged cross-correlations or co-activation patterns to infer functional interactions. Recent developments also include the use of machine learning architectures such as autoencoders and graph neural networks¹⁷.

An alternative strategy is to infer networks by fitting mechanistic or generative models to data. These include symbolic regression approaches¹⁸, manifold reconstruction techniques¹⁹, compressive sensing²⁰, and machine-learning-based models^{21,22}. Applications in neuroscience have driven much of this progress, yet the field faces persistent challenges: neural signals propagate with delays, are spatially and temporally subsampled, and often arise from systems far from equilibrium.

Despite these advances, many methods rely on strong assumptions –such as sparsity, linearity, or the availability of long time series or large datasets–and often require detailed prior knowledge to specify model parameters (e.g., specific time delays)^{23,24}. Moreover, direct measurement of network links is frequently infeasible or invasive, as in brain connectomics, and in many experimental contexts only a subset of relevant variables can be measured. This leads to incomplete or coarse-grained mathematical descriptions of the system under study.

To address these limitations, we introduce a method capable of inferring the structure

of a network exclusively from multivariate time series data, without the need for interventions, explicit mechanistic models, or strong prior assumptions. Our approach builds on the Reservoir Computing (RC) paradigm –a class of recurrent neural networks with fixed internal dynamics and trainable output layers. We propose a novel architectural modification, which we call subReservoir Computing (sRC), in which each node in the observed network is assigned an independent subReservoir. These subReservoirs are decoupled during training, except through a shared output layer that integrates their dynamics.

Each subReservoir nonlinearly transforms the input time series into a high-dimensional representation, enabling the output layer to learn predictive mappings among nodes. Crucially, by inspecting the trained weights of the output layer, we extract the inferred causal interactions. This modular architecture allows for robust, scalable network reconstruction while relaxing many of the limitations of previous approaches.

Results

Dynamical system reconstruction in Reservoir Computing

The Reservoir Computing computational model is based on a high-dimensional nonlinear dynamical system –the reservoir– driven by the time series or similar ordered sequences under investigation. The inputs are projected into the reservoir at the locations specified by a fixed input layer matrix \mathbf{W}_{in} (Figure 1). Owing to its rich, nonlinear dynamics, the reservoir can transform input signals $\mathbf{u}(t)$ into a high-dimensional representation suitable for solving complex tasks. The resulting state of the reservoir $\mathbf{r}(t)$ is read out through a trainable output layer matrix \mathbf{W}_{out} , which is optimised for a specific objective.

In most implementations, the reservoir is instantiated as a recurrent neural network, where the states of the reservoir nodes are recursively updated using both the external input and the network’s own past states. Unlike in other neural network architectures, the input and reservoir weight matrices are randomly initialized and kept fixed, i.e. they are not trained. Learning is restricted to the linear output readout layer, which is optimised to minimize the prediction error between the output and the target time series. This is typically achieved through a Least Squares minimization on the output weight matrix:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{r}(t+1) &= f(\mathbf{W}\mathbf{r}(t) + \mathbf{W}_{in}\mathbf{u}(t)) \\ \hat{\mathbf{u}}(t+1) &= \mathbf{W}_{out}\mathbf{r}(t+1)\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

$$L = \frac{1}{T} \sum \|\mathbf{u}(t_i) - \hat{\mathbf{u}}(t_i)\|^2 + \lambda \sum \|\mathbf{W}_{out}\|^2$$

The most common use of Reservoir Computing is for time series prediction, where the network is trained to forecast the next value in a sequence, effectively learning to emulate the underlying dynamical system^{25,26,27,28}. Once trained, the Reservoir Computer can be transformed into an autonomous dynamical system by feeding its own output back as input, thereby generating trajectories that closely reproduce the original dynamics.

Recent theoretical work has shown that Reservoir Computing systems are universal approximators of dynamical systems, provided certain conditions are met^{25,26}. These include ensuring that the reservoir has sufficient dimensionality and that the dynamics exhibit fading memory, often enforced by constraining the spectral radius of \mathbf{W} to $\rho(\mathbf{W}) \leq 1$. Underlying this powerful capability is the ability to attain Generalized Synchronization, meaning that the states of the reservoir $\mathbf{r}(t)$, hold a one-to-one relationship with the states of the original system, $\mathbf{s}(t)$. Reservoir Computing can be viewed as embedding time series data into a high-dimensional space, reminiscent of delay-coordinate embeddings based on Takens' theorem^{28,29}. In delay-coordinate embeddings, state-space reconstructions are obtained by stacking delayed versions of an observed variable; under appropriate conditions, the resulting trajectories are diffeomorphic to those of the original system. Similarly, Reservoir Computing can learn meaningful representations from incomplete data—even when some system variables are unobserved—by leveraging its internal memory to capture relevant dynamics^{30,31,32,33}. However, the true power of Reservoir Computing lies in its ability to embed not just a specific time series but also the putative dynamical rules governing such series. In effect, the hypothetical dynamical system underlying a process is embedded into a much higher-dimensional space, where it can be analyzed and later reduced to a more interpretable model.

Architecture of the subReservoir computational model

We introduce a conceptual change in the architecture of Reservoir Computing computers to make the model apt to encode and reveal, in its output layer, the causal links between the time series stemming from the nodes of a network of dynamical systems. In our proposal, the Eqs. 1 remain valid, and only the matrices \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{W}_{in} are structured as block-sparse. Each of the blocks is built largely as an individual reservoirs (see Fig. 1b). This architecture modification has the purpose of controlling the flow of infor-

mation from the inputs to the reservoir, and from the reservoir to the outputs, so that the information flow from different nodes is not mixed until the output layer. The output layer W_{out} is trained following the same training procedure as in Reservoir Computing, by least-squares regression using the complete set of nodes. Within each subReservoir, time series are expanded in a multidimensional state space that is an embedding of the state space where the time series lives. Therefore, the other dimensions of the time series that are needed for their interaction with the other nodes are automatically reconstructed within the subReservoir, albeit in a hidden way. After training, the subset of weights that connect each subReservoir to a specific output node encodes the contribution of this sub-Reservoir to the predicted output of the node. Since the loss function contains a ridge term that induces shrinkage of weights, during training the weights of the output layer that are important for prediction are enhanced, while the others will be suppressed. We can exploit from this principle by inspecting the weights of the output layer and determining, based on their values after regression, which ones are predicted to correspond to a link (Fig. 1b right).

Figure 1 Computational model of Reservoir Computing and subReservoir Computing. a Standard architecture of Reservoir Computing. Consecutive values of a time series $u(t)$, obtained as measurements from an evolving dynamical system whose state $s(t)$ may not be directly accessible, are sequentially presented as inputs, driving the reservoir through the input weights W_{in} . The reservoir, in turn, updates its

states recursively via the recurrent connections \mathbf{W} . Training is restricted to the output layer weights \mathbf{W}_{out} , which are optimized to predict future values of $u(t)$ based on the reservoir states $\mathbf{r}(t)$. Once trained, the network can be transformed into an autonomous dynamical system by feeding back its output into its input. The resulting trajectories can then be used for tasks such as time series forecasting and attractor reconstruction. **b** Architecture and steps proposed in the subReservoir Computing scheme for network inference. The networked dynamical system is accessible only through node-level measurements, while its structural connectivity remains hidden. Time series from individual nodes drive separate reservoirs (subReservoirs) which at this stage are uncoupled. A fully connected output layer \mathbf{W}_{out} is trained using the states generated by all subReservoirs. The structure of subReservoir Computing allows the *a posteriori* inspection of the output layer weights, revealing the contribution of each input time series to each (predicted) output time series. Each subset $\mathbf{W}_{out(i,j)}$, which links the subReservoir of node i to output of node j is used to infer the existence of a directed link $i \rightarrow j$ in the original dynamical system. Scalar measures, such as the norm, can be applied for this purpose, resulting in an adjacency matrix or graph.

Inference on a network of synthetic neurons

In order to test the hypothesis that subReservoir Computing can be used to infer the structure of dynamical networks, we simulated 10 seconds of activity from a group of 20 noisy Hodgkin–Huxley neurons, connected in a ring topology (see Methods), and analyzed the corresponding multivariate time series of the membrane potential $v(t)$ using the subReservoir Computing method (Fig. 2). The results show that the subReservoir Computer can learn the connections between nodes in the distribution of weights of the output layer, which can be used to identify links in the dynamical network. Specifically, when there is a connection in the dynamical network from node i to node j , the corresponding entries of the output layer weight matrix $\mathbf{W}_{out(i,j)}$ display a broader distribution, indicating that some of its entries are fitted to higher values. Conversely, when the connection is absent, the corresponding values of the output layer cluster close to zero. To quantify this self-organization process, we defined a scalar measure, the variance, to quantify the distribution of weights in the output layer. The non-binary inferred adjacency matrix $A_{i,j}$ was computed as $A_{i,j} = \text{var}(\mathbf{W}_{out(i,j)})$ (compare with original network in Fig. 2). The distribution of matrix $A_{i,j}$ shows a clear bimodal distribution, indicating that groups of entries that are necessary for predicting a certain output evolve towards higher absolute values. This bimodal distribution allows for a well-defined threshold T to classify an entry as a link with $A_{i,j}^* = \mathcal{H}(A_{i,j} - T)$, where $\mathcal{H}(\cdot)$ is the Heaviside function. We observed that the cluster identification was more effective on the values of $A_{i,j}$ in logarithmic scale. We obtained comparable results in calculating the scalar magnitudes $A_{i,j}$ with different norms and measures, and used the variance as a simple and effective measure. The procedure to reconstruct the network of a dynamical system from the time series of its nodes is detailed in Algorithm 1.

To estimate a suitable threshold T , various classification algorithms can be applied,

Algorithm 1 subReservoir Computing network inference.

```
initialize subReservoir Computing with hyperparameters
if sRC is fully connected then
  redefine  $\mathbf{W}_{in}$  and  $\mathbf{W}$  as block-sparse with  $N$  blocks
end if
while  $t \leq t_{max}$  do
  drive reservoirs states  $\mathbf{r}(t)$  with  $\mathbf{r}(t+1) = f(\mathbf{W}\mathbf{r}(t) + \mathbf{W}_{in}\mathbf{v}(t))$ 
end while
train  $\mathbf{W}_{out}$  by minimizing  $L = \frac{1}{T} \sum \|\mathbf{v}(t_i) - \hat{\mathbf{v}}(t_i)\|^2 + \lambda \sum \|\mathbf{W}_{out}\|^2$ 
group  $\mathbf{W}_{out}$  entries in  $N \times N$  blocks as  $\mathbf{W}_{out(i,j)}$ 
for  $i = 1 \dots N$  do
  for  $j = 1 \dots N$  do
    compute non-binary adjacency matrix  $A_{i,j} = \text{measure}(\mathbf{W}_{out(i,j)})$ 
  end for
end for
compute threshold  $T$  for classification from  $A$  statistics
for  $i = 1 \dots N$  do
  for  $j = 1 \dots N$  do
    compute binary adjacency matrix  $A^*$  as link/no link with  $A_{i,j}^* = \mathcal{H}(A_{i,j} - T)$ 
  end for
end for
```

including Otsu's method³⁴, Gaussian mixture models³⁵ and density-based clustering^{36,37}. However, we employed a simple method based on quantile analysis. By partitioning the set of values $\log(A_{i,j})$ into equal parts, we computed the difference between consecutive quantiles, which is expected to be larger in regions between clusters. Local maxima in this difference curve were then selected as candidates for threshold T . This method appears to be particularly effective for unbalanced clusters (see Supp. Material).

Figure 2 subReservoir Computing infers neuronal networks from synthetic data. **a** Exploratory example network consisting of 20 four-dimensional Hodgkin-Huxley model neurons connected in a ring topology. Each neuron is subjected to noise and coupling with other neurons through the specified network. Only the variable v is considered accessible and is used for inference. **b** Time series generated by simulating 10 seconds of activity from the 20 coupled noisy Hodgkin-Huxley neurons. The vertical axis in each plot correspond to the membrane potential in mV. Scales are omitted for clarity, since the focus is on collective dynamics rather than absolute values. **c** Each time series is used to drive individual subReservoirs and train a fully-connected output layer. **d** (left) Distribution of output layer weights W_{out} in the subReservoir Computer, obtained from learning on data generated by the network represented by the adjacency matrix. Subsets of weights whose distribution is plotted are marked with red symbols. Weights corresponding to true connections in the adjacency matrix follow broader distribution (marked in black). For node pairs (i, j) not connected in the original system, the distribution is narrow, indicating minimal contribution to the predicted output. Weights corresponding to self-connections are omitted and replaced with gray rectangles for clarity. (right) The non-binary inferred adjacency matrix $A_{i,j}$ is computing as the variance of $W_{out}(i,j)$. The distribution of $A_{i,j}$ entries is bimodal, allowing each (i, j) to be assigned to one of two clusters. High-

value entries correspond to bright colors in the $A_{i,j}$ representation. By applying the Heaviside function $\mathcal{H}(A_{i,j} - T)$ the inferred adjacency matrix $A_{i,j}^*$ is obtained.

Robustness of the method for different networks

To assess the robustness of our network inference method, we explored its performance on a range of different network topologies. We simulated the dynamical evolution of networks of coupled chaotic Lorenz systems³⁸ (see Methods) with various topologies, including ring, bidirectional ring, and random networks (Fig. 3). Our results show that the subReservoir Computing method can accurately infer the network structure in all four cases, with no errors. This suggests that the method is robust and can handle a diverse range of network topologies, from well-structured rings to random networks. Further numerical tests support this conclusion, indicating that the method is likely to be effective for a wide range of network topologies.

Figure 3 Diverse network topologies of Lorenz systems inferred with subReservoir Computing. Different connectivity patterns, with different density of connections, can be inferred using the same method without additional hyper-parameter tuning. The examples shown achieve perfect reconstruction, and the method also identifies mutual coupling. From left to right: simple ring-ordered network, double-directed ring-ordered network, double-connected ring-ordered network and random network with 50% of links. For the random network, the inference of A^* is shown for clarity.

To further investigate the robustness of our method, we tested its performance on networks of varying sizes (Fig. 4a) and with three different dynamical systems, namely

Lorenz system³⁸, Hodgkin-Huxley neurons³⁹ and Izhikevich neurons⁴⁰. Our results show that the distribution of $A_{i,j}$ values exhibits a similar clustering behavior for both large and small networks. Moreover, we observed that this behavior is consistent across three different dynamical systems, despite their distinct characteristics and numbers of latent variables. Very frequently, systems are subjected to a finite speed of propagation of information. In Fig. 4b, we show an example of inference on data in which coupling between two given nodes arrives to the target node with a delay of 50 time steps in the simulation. No further hyperparameter tuning was performed with respect to the non-delayed case. While the reconstruction is of poorer quality compared to the previous examples, it illustrates the power of the method. This set of results suggests that the organization of the $A_{i,j}$ values is relatively independent of the network size and the specific dynamical system being studied.

a. Scaling network sizes

b. Inference with coupling delays

Figure 4 subReservoir Computing enables versatile network inference. **a** Networks of different sizes and from different dynamical systems are accurately recovered with very low errors rates. Examples include networks ranging from 5 to 80 nodes, simulated using three different dynamical systems. **b** Inference can be also performed under the existence of delays in the coupling between nodes in the original dynamical system, thanks to the memory properties of the reservoir. An example is shown for a system with a 50-time-step delay.

Discussion

We introduced a novel method for inferring networks in dynamical systems, which we term subReservoir Computing. This approach builds upon the principles of Reservoir Computing, a class of recurrent neural networks, and modifies its architecture to create a computing scheme that can learn and infer network structures from time series data. In subReservoir Computing, each node in the dynamical system is associated with a subReservoir that expands the time series into a high-dimensional space, generating embeddings that are used to train a fully connected readout layer that predicts future values of each time series taking into account all subReservoirs. After learning, the readout layer encodes the existence of links between nodes in the dynamical system in its own weights. We observed that this encoding is manifested through the self-organization process in which the measures of the collective entries from each reservoir to each other output node group into two clusters, with the cluster having high mean values indicating the existence of links. Our method inherits attributes of Reservoir Computing associated with the theory of delay embeddings and the universal approximation properties of neural networks, which enable it to reconstruct arbitrary dynamical systems. We demonstrated the versatility of our method in tackling inference from time series generated by different dynamical systems, with different network topologies, and with different sizes.

Previous work has addressed the inference of networks using variants of machine learning based on neural networks^{17,21,22,24}. Feed-forward neural networks^{17,21} often require computationally intensive optimization of internal parameters via back-propagation, relying on the availability of substantial amounts of data. In contrast, our subReservoir Computing method leverages the advantages of Reservoir Computing, which only requires the optimization of the readout layer using a one-shot analytic solution. This advantage was previously used to infer short-term interactions using a fully connected Reservoir Computing²², by computing an estimation of the partial derivatives of the outputs with respect to the inputs. This method is limited to interactions that propagate with speed comparable to one time step, but it was extended to account for delays²⁴ by scanning for an optimal delay within a range. This requires previous knowledge of the dynamics and potential delays in the system under study. Furthermore, since the reservoirs used are

fully connected, their method suffers from scaling problems posed by the size of the reservoir required to embed high-dimensional time series. This is solved in our method, which uses individual subReservoirs driven by each of the nodes separately, inducing a linear scalability of the method with respect to the number of nodes in the original network. This is reminiscent of a previous approach that used parallel reservoirs for forecasting large systems⁴¹, profiting from their linear scalability and small size of individual reservoirs. However, in their approach the interconnection between individual reservoirs is assessed separately with a different method. Our method assesses the interconnection between individual reservoirs directly, without the need for a separate method.

Real-world systems are often undersampled with respect to the relevant variables⁴², making it challenging to infer their underlying network structures. However, our subReservoir Computing method is equipped with embedding mechanisms that allow it to handle these complexities. A key feature is the Generalized Synchronization, which enable the internal reconstruction of non-accessed variables in a high-dimensional space, effectively expanding the available information. We demonstrated this robustness in our first exploratory example, where we inferred the network structure of a four-dimensional system (Hodgkin-Huxley neurons) using only one of its variables. Furthermore, we showed that our method can naturally handle the presence of noise and interaction delays, which are common features of real-world systems. These findings suggest that our subReservoir Computing method is a powerful tool for robustly processing data from actual applications, even in the presence of non-idealized conditions.

Methods

Data generation

To evaluate the method developed here, we resort to datasets where the underlying network is perfectly known and we have grounds to compare the reconstruction. This is generally challenging in experimental datasets, since it requires either the controlled assembly of the network before the experiment, or a careful reconstruction with an undisputed method – most likely invasive or destructive. We therefore follow a tactic that resembles the controlled assembly of the network, although we do it *in silico*. We created datasets with three well-known model sets of differential equations, which are modified to include interaction terms and noise. The intensity of noise in all models is controlled with parameter σ_{dyn} , and coupling between nodes is done with the matrix entries $\alpha_{i,j}$, which are zero in absence of connections. Solutions of the neuronal models were obtained with scripts written using the NEST library⁴³, while the Lorenz model with a in-house implementation of numerical integration based on the system implemented in Ref.²².

Lorenz attractor The Lorenz model is a three-variable canonical model for the study of chaotic dynamics³⁸. The parameters are set such that the model behaves chaotically.

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}_i &= 10(y_i - x_i) + 3 \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_{i,j} (y_j - y_i) + \sigma_{dyn} \eta_x \\ \dot{y}_i &= 28x_i - y_i - x_i z_i + \sigma_{dyn} \eta_y \\ \dot{z}_i &= x_i y_i - \frac{8}{3} z_i + \sigma_{dyn} \eta_z\end{aligned}$$

Hodgkin-Huxley Neurons The Hodgkin-Huxley is a canonical, four-variable, biophysically realistic model of neurons³⁹.

$$\begin{aligned}C\dot{v}_i &= -g_K n_i^4 (v - E_K) - g_{Na} m_i^3 h_i (v - E_{Na}) - g_L (v - E_L) + I_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_{i,j} I_{incoming,j} + \sigma_{dyn} \eta_v \\ \dot{n}_i &= \alpha_n(v) (1 - n_i) - \beta_n(v) n_i \\ \dot{m}_i &= \alpha_m(v) (1 - m_i) - \beta_m(v) m_i \\ \dot{h}_i &= \alpha_h(v) (1 - h_i) - \beta_h(v) h_i\end{aligned}$$

Izhikevich Neurons The Izhikevich model is a two-variable model with reset that is designed to reproduce many features in the dynamics of neurons with a low dimensional model⁴⁰. The reset mechanism is added an auxiliary after-spike forcing, which introduces further nonlinearities.

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{v}_i &= 0.04 v^2 + 5v + 140u - I_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_{i,j} I_{incoming,j} + \sigma_{dyn} \eta_v \\ \dot{u}_i &= 0.2(0.02v - u) \\ \text{if } v > 30 &\text{ then } v \leftarrow -65.0 \quad ; \quad u \leftarrow u + 6.0\end{aligned}$$

Implementation subReservoir Computing

In the numerical examples shown in this manuscript, each subReservoir is constructed using 150 internal units, each of the with an spectral radius of 0.9, and trained using 30000 time steps of the time series. Ridge regularization was set to $\lambda = 10^{-4}$. As no hyperparameter optimization was performed for the different examples of application, we suggest that the provided scheme can be improved for better performance in different instances.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft through the Grant No. RTG 2749/1 “Biological Clocks on Multiple Time Scales”. M. E. G. and P. R. acknowledge University of Kassel through ZFF-PROJEKT 2377 and the Graduate Program Biological Clocks. O. P. acknowledges COST Action CA21169, the MICIN Mobility Contract No. PRX22/00522, and the Maria de Maeztu Grant No. CEX2021-001198-M funded by MCIN/AEI. P. R. acknowledges support from the Joachim Herz Foundation.

References

- [1] Barabási, A.-L. Network science. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* **371**, 20120375 (2013).
- [2] Peters, J., Janzing, D. & Schölkopf, B. *Elements of causal inference: foundations and learning algorithms* (The MIT Press, 2017).
- [3] Runge, J. Causal network reconstruction from time series: From theoretical assumptions to practical estimation. *Chaos: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Nonlinear Science* **28** (2018).
- [4] Stepaniants, G., Brunton, B. W. & Kutz, J. N. Inferring causal networks of dynamical systems through transient dynamics and perturbation. *Physical Review E* **102**, 042309 (2020).
- [5] Mooij, J. M., Peters, J., Janzing, D., Zscheischler, J. & Schölkopf, B. Distinguishing cause from effect using observational data: methods and benchmarks. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* **17**, 1–102 (2016).
- [6] Granger, C. W. Investigating causal relations by econometric models and cross-spectral methods. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society* 424–438 (1969).
- [7] Kim, S., Putrino, D., Ghosh, S. & Brown, E. N. A granger causality measure for point process models of ensemble neural spiking activity. *PLoS computational biology* **7**, e1001110 (2011).
- [8] Gerhard, F. *et al.* Successful reconstruction of a physiological circuit with known connectivity from spiking activity alone. *PLoS computational biology* **9**, e1003138 (2013).
- [9] Schreiber, T. Measuring information transfer. *Physical Review Letters* **85**, 461 (2000).

- [10] Vicente, R., Wibral, M., Lindner, M. & Pipa, G. Transfer entropy—a model-free measure of effective connectivity for the neurosciences. *Journal of computational neuroscience* **30**, 45–67 (2011).
- [11] Chen, Y., Rosen, B. Q. & Sejnowski, T. J. Dynamical differential covariance recovers directional network structure in multiscale neural systems. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **119**, e2117234119 (2022).
- [12] Lin, T. W., Das, A., Krishnan, G. P., Bazhenov, M. & Sejnowski, T. J. Differential covariance: A new class of methods to estimate sparse connectivity from neural recordings. *Neural computation* **29**, 2581–2632 (2017).
- [13] Das, A. & Fiete, I. R. Systematic errors in connectivity inferred from activity in strongly recurrent networks. *Nature Neuroscience* **23**, 1286–1296 (2020).
- [14] Stylianou, O. *et al.* Multiscale detrended cross-correlation coefficient: Estimating coupling in nonstationary neurophysiological signals. *bioRxiv* (2024). <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2024/04/19/2024.04.16.589689.full.pdf>.
- [15] Giusti, C., Pastalkova, E., Curto, C. & Itskov, V. Clique topology reveals intrinsic geometric structure in neural correlations. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **112**, 13455–13460 (2015).
- [16] Quaglio, P., Rostami, V., Torre, E. & Grün, S. Methods for identification of spike patterns in massively parallel spike trains. *Biological Cybernetics* **112**, 57–80 (2018).
- [17] Kipf, T., Fetaya, E., Wang, K.-C., Welling, M. & Zemel, R. Neural relational inference for interacting systems. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, 2688–2697 (PMLR, 2018).
- [18] Mangan, N. M., Brunton, S. L., Proctor, J. L. & Kutz, J. N. Inferring biological networks by sparse identification of nonlinear dynamics. *IEEE Transactions on Molecular, Biological, and Multi-Scale Communications* **2**, 52–63 (2016).
- [19] Casadiego, J., Nitzan, M., Hallerberg, S. & Timme, M. Model-free inference of direct network interactions from nonlinear collective dynamics. *Nature Communications* **8**, 2192 (2017).
- [20] Kathpalia, A. & Nagaraj, N. Granger causality for compressively sensed sparse signals. *Physical Review E* **107**, 034308 (2023).
- [21] Tank, A., Covert, I., Foti, N., Shojaie, A. & Fox, E. B. Neural granger causality. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* **44**, 4267–4279 (2021).

- [22] Banerjee, A., Pathak, J., Roy, R., Restrepo, J. G. & Ott, E. Using machine learning to assess short term causal dependence and infer network links. *Chaos: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Nonlinear Science* **29** (2019).
- [23] Topal, I. & Eroglu, D. Reconstructing network dynamics of coupled discrete chaotic units from data. *Physical Review Letters* **130**, 117401 (2023).
- [24] Banerjee, A., Hart, J. D., Roy, R. & Ott, E. Machine learning link inference of noisy delay-coupled networks with optoelectronic experimental tests. *Physical Review X* **11**, 031014 (2021).
- [25] Grigoryeva, L. & Ortega, J.-P. Echo state networks are universal. *Neural Networks* **108**, 495–508 (2018).
- [26] Gonon, L., Grigoryeva, L. & Ortega, J.-P. Approximation bounds for random neural networks and reservoir systems. *The Annals of Applied Probability* **33**, 28–69 (2023).
- [27] Grigoryeva, L., Hart, A. & Ortega, J.-P. Learning strange attractors with reservoir systems. *Nonlinearity* **36**, 4674 (2023).
- [28] Hart, A., Hook, J. & Dawes, J. Embedding and approximation theorems for echo state networks. *Neural Networks* **128**, 234–247 (2020).
- [29] Takens, F. Detecting strange attractors in turbulence. In *Lecture Notes in Mathematics: Dynamical Systems of Turbulence*, 366–381 (Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1981).
- [30] Lu, Z., Hunt, B. R. & Ott, E. Attractor reconstruction by machine learning. *Chaos: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Nonlinear Science* **28** (2018).
- [31] Pathak, J., Lu, Z., Hunt, B. R., Girvan, M. & Ott, E. Using machine learning to replicate chaotic attractors and calculate lyapunov exponents from data. *Chaos: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Nonlinear Science* **27** (2017).
- [32] Lu, Z. *et al.* Reservoir observers: Model-free inference of unmeasured variables in chaotic systems. *Chaos: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Nonlinear Science* **27** (2017).
- [33] Pathak, J., Hunt, B., Girvan, M., Lu, Z. & Ott, E. Model-free prediction of large spatiotemporally chaotic systems from data: A reservoir computing approach. *Physical review letters* **120**, 024102 (2018).
- [34] Otsu, N. A threshold selection method from gray-level histograms. *IEEE transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics* **9**, 62–66 (1979).
- [35] Baxter, R. A. *Mixture Model.*, 680–682 (Springer US, 2010).
- [36] Rodriguez, A. & Laio, A. Clustering by fast search and find of density peaks. *science* **344**, 1492–1496 (2014).

- [37] Schubert, E., Sander, J., Ester, M., Kriegel, H. P. & Xu, X. Dbscan revisited, revisited: why and how you should (still) use dbscan. *ACM Transactions on Database Systems (TODS)* **42**, 1–21 (2017).
- [38] Lorenz, E. N. Deterministic nonperiodic flow. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences* **20**, 130 (1963).
- [39] Hodgkin, A. L. & Huxley, A. F. A quantitative description of membrane current and its application to conduction and excitation in nerve. *The Journal of physiology* **117**, 500 (1952).
- [40] Izhikevich, E. M. *Dynamical systems in neuroscience* (MIT press, 2007).
- [41] Srinivasan, K. *et al.* Parallel machine learning for forecasting the dynamics of complex networks. *Physical Review Letters* **128**, 164101 (2022).
- [42] Levina, A., Priesemann, V. & Zierenberg, J. Tackling the subsampling problem to infer collective properties from limited data. *Nature Reviews Physics* **4**, 770–784 (2022).
- [43] Fardet, T. *et al.* Nest 2.20.0 (2020). URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3605514>.